

EcoStack

Handbook

Policy options for exploitation
of functional biodiversity

Edited by Antonio Paparella

Authors: Antonio Paparella, Hanna Frieberg, Xavier Sans Sierra, Luigi Cembalo, Teresa Del Giudice, Bettina Wenzel, Hella Kehlenbeck

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION	3
DOCUMENT REVISION HISTORY	ERRORE. IL SEGNALIBRO NON È DEFINITO.
1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. THE ECOSTACK KNOWLEDGE BANK	4
3. POLICY AND POLICY OPTIONS	5
4. CONCLUSIONS	27
REFERENCES	28

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Authors	Antonio Paparella (UNA), Hanna Frieberg (SLU), Xavier Sans Sierra (UB), Luigi Cembalo (UNA), Teresa Del Giudice (UNA), Bettina Wenzel (JKI), Hella Kehlenbeck (JKI)
Affiliations:	UNA: University of Naples Federico II, Italy SLU: Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Sweden BU: Universitat de Barcelona, Spain JKI: Julius Kühn-Institut - Federal Research Centre for Cultivated Plants, Quedlinburg, Germany

Portici (IT), 2024

1. Introduction

The overall objective of EcoStack is to develop and support ecologically, economically and socially sustainable crop protection via enhancement of ecosystem services provision and protection of functional biodiversity. Intensification of agriculture to meet food demands of a growing global population is difficult to reconcile with protection of the environment and of non-renewable resources. The resulting loss of natural habitats through conversion into farmland with intensive farming has major negative impacts on the environment and biodiversity; a serious concern addressed by a number of EU agri-environment policies. Moreover, the use of synthetic agrochemicals is often associated with undesirable negative impacts, which are addressed by the EU Directive on Sustainable Use of Pesticides (Directive 2009/128/EC).

Agroecosystems are ecologically simplified and artificially managed, but they still rely on multiple ecosystem services provided by a wealth of beneficial organisms and microorganisms, which are essential for biocontrol of pests, pollination of crops, recycling of nutrients and organic matter for maintenance of soil fertility, and conservation of farmland biodiversity. EcoStack is a multi-actor endeavor, aiming at developing ecologically, economically and socially sustainable crop production strategies via stacking of ecosystem service provision from optimized biodiversity management and bio-inspired tools for crop protection, in order to enhance the sustainability of food production systems across Europe.

This document serves as a holistic exploration of the project's multifaceted policy implications, merging together narratives from farmers, policymakers, and scholars. At the cutting edge of research, impressive efforts and notable results have been achieved to fulfill this goal. Initially, a conspicuous volume of scientific documents stands as evidence of the effective work carried out throughout the project's duration. Moreover, ancillary but essential tasks co-generated value from the scientific results. The organization of workshops, the establishment of a knowledge bank, and other dissemination activities made possible to foster the diffusion and adoption of the sustainable practices developed. However, ECOSTACK scientific results represent a wealth of information able, on one side, to feed policies in terms of potential tools to be selected and, on the other side, without policy tools, the scientific results risk to be disseminated slowly lowering their potential results on the society.

To that end, the current document aims at proposing policy options that take stock of ECOSTACK results, including stakeholders' opinion on the current and future CAP, as well as of the recent European socio-economic scenario with, in mind, the critical role policies play in facilitating the widespread adoption of sustainable practices.

2. The EcoStack Knowledge Bank

Before starting describing the specific contribution on policy options, a brief description of the ECOSTACK knowledge bank is necessary since it represents a unique (all information in one place) tool to share the ECOSTACK results to stakeholders. Available on the web, it was built taking in mind readability and searchability.

The Knowledge Bank consists of Best Practice Sheets, User Manuals, Informative Videos, Green Week presentations, newsletters, and a list of scientific papers supporting the most relevant results. A brief description of Best Practice Sheets, User manual, and Newsletters is provided here.

The Best Practice Sheets

The Best Practice Sheets are produced to help farmers and stakeholders have direct access to the agronomic feedback of the ECOSTACK research findings, identifying advisable agronomic options for different agricultural contexts. The Best Practices Sheets cover the following agronomic practices: intercropping cereal and legume crops, companion cropping in oilseeds to control insect pests, organic mulching in potato fields to enhance ecosystem regulation services, crop cultivar mixtures to enhance insect biocontrol, and combined biological control with microorganism and biofumigation in soil-based tomato production disease control.

The User Manuals

Some User Manuals are provided. User Manuals are documents briefly explaining the ECOSTACK agronomic practices made accessible to farmers or anyone interested via the Knowledge Bank. The agronomic measures defined in the Users Manuals are the use of organic mulching in potato fields to control insect pests and provide ecosystem services, intercropping cereals and legumes to enhance ecosystem services provision, companion cropping to control insect pests in oilseed fields, and crop cultivar mixtures to enhance insect biocontrol.

Green Week presentation

EU Green Week is an annual opportunity to debate European environmental policy with policymakers, leading environmentalists and stakeholders from Europe and beyond. The 2022 edition focused on the European Green Deal - the EU's sustainable and transformative growth strategy for a resource-efficient and climate-neutral Europe by 2050. In this event, results and insight from the ECOSTACK project were presented and discussed with stakeholders. The presentations are available and part of the Knowledge Bank.

5

The Newsletter

As part of the Knowledge Bank, the ECOSTACK project publishes a regular newsletter aimed at disseminating key findings and updates to farmers and stakeholders. The newsletter serves as an essential communication tool, sharing the latest developments, success stories, and practical insights from the project in an accessible and engaging manner.

3. Policy and policy options

In this chapter, the alignment of ECOSTACK agronomic measures with Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) objectives and potential policy options are explored. Insights and remarks from surveys conducted with farmers and policymakers are reported here. Results underscore the need for nuanced policy considerations to foster widespread adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. Moreover, the perspective of ECOSTACK

experts conjoins the analysis, developing possible policy options and discussing strengths and weaknesses of the ECOSTACK measures policy integration.

3.1. Policy-makers perspective on ECOSTACK measures

In tandem with collecting the farmers' opinions, the ECOSTACK project also sought the perspectives of policymakers about the ECOSTACK measures. In order to accomplish that, policymakers at various levels, encompassing national, regional, and European Union authorities were interviewed. The objective was to gain a comprehensive understanding of how the measures developed within ECOSTACK align with existing policies and to explore potential future broader adoption and integration into the current agricultural policy.

3.1.1. The panel

The recruitment was carried out within the ECOSTACK project. The academic members of the project were asked to propose experts in agrifood policy or people involved in agrifood policy development in the European context at different scales. Both local and communitarian policymakers were contacted. The final number of experts who accepted to participate was fifteen. The experts represented four different European countries: Germany, Italy, Spain and Sweden as shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1 – Highlighted the Countries represented by the panel of policymakers.

3.1.2. The policymakers opinion

Here, the results of the analysis of the answers to the questionnaire are presented. The panel was presented with the general aims and objectives of the ECOSTACK project. Then, it was asked to respond to two main points relative to the ECOSTACK measures. First, the policymakers indicated the importance they give to each of the ECOSTACK measures on a scale from 1 (=not important) to 7 (=very important). Second, they indicated the policy structure where the measure can or could find the best implementation. The policy structures were the main components of the Common Agricultural Policy. Those are Agro-climatic-environmental interventions, Eco-schemes and Enhanced cross-compliance. Results are shown in Fig 2 and Fig 3.

Fig 2 – EcoStack measure importance for policymakers on a scale from 1 (=not important) to 7 (=very important).

Fig 3 – Suggested policy structure for the EcoStack measures by policymakers.

As it emerges from Fig 5, policymakers give a high level of importance to all the ECOSTACK measures; the average importance is around 5 out of 7. The most important measures for the policymakers are "Biological control" and "Diversified crop rotation". On the other hand, the least important are "Cultivar mixture", "Organic mulches", and "Intercropping". Also, information about the variability of the responses is reported. The most consensual measure is "Biological control", and the least is "Intercropping". The policymakers' opinion on the alignment of the measure to the CAP structure is highlighted and discussed in paragraph 3.4.2.

3.2. Analysis of how ECOSTACK measures align with CAP objectives

Assessing the alignment of the ECOSTACK agronomic measures with the existing Common Agricultural Policy is of crucial importance. The effectiveness of the measures in terms of environmental benefits can be scaled up when adopted on a large scale. Clearly, the diffusion of the measures is enhanced by policy support via economic remuneration or other support types. For this reason, understanding the integration of the ECOSTACK measures into the EU agricultural policy is fundamental to building up policy options.

3.2.1. The expert opinion

Within the study conducted involving policymakers (discussed in detail in the previous paragraph), a measure of the alignment of the practices was collected by the experts. They were asked, for each ECOSTACK measure,

to indicate the policy structure where it belongs. The possible alternatives were Agro-Climatic-Environmental Interventions, Eco-schemes, and Enhanced cross-compliance. Also, they could choose "Don't know" as a possible answer. The results are shown in Figure 3 (see 3.1.2). As we can see from Figure 3, the responses are significantly diversified both in terms of individual answers and different policy structures chosen for the measures.

The only ECOSTACK measure where the panel had a consistent agreement was the use of Flowering Strips in the Enhanced Cross-Compliance. Opposite consideration for Diversified crop rotation and Biological control, where the answers were diversified almost uniformly across the different options. Shifting the attention to how the policy structures scored, Eco-schemes appear to be the favoured category for many measures, with relatively high responses for practices like Cover Crops, Organic Mulches, and Intercropping. The frequent choice of the "Don't Know" category highlights the complexity of the task. The lack of consensus in this category suggests that experts may find it challenging to place some practices within a single policy structure definitively.

3.3. Analysis of how the CAP 2023-2027 planned interventions can support ECOSTACK strategies

3.4. Farmers' adoption and opinion

3.4.1. The survey and the sample

The ECOSTACK project focuses on developing environmentally friendly practices, the success of which is determined by diffusion across the EU farmer population. Hence, it is crucial to delve into the farmer's perspective of the developed ECOSTACK strategies. By directly engaging those who practice agriculture, the survey provides valuable insights into the real-world implications and acceptance of the ECOSTACK strategies. For these reasons, within the ECOSTACK project, a sample of farmers from various EU countries has been interviewed to explore their opinions and preferences about the ECOSTACK results. The sample consists of 278 farmers in total. In Fig 4, the countries represented by the sample. Those are Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Sweden, and the United Kingdom. Also, Table 1 shows the sample distribution by country.

Fig 4 – Highlighted the Countries represented by the sample.

Country	Interviewed Farmers
Austria	2
Bulgaria	5
Finland	93
France	33
Germany	80
Italy	48
Sweden	7
United Kingdom	10

Tab 1 – Sample distribution by country.

Moreover, the sample sociodemographic and structural characteristics of the farm managed by the interviewed are listed in Table 2 and Table 3.

	Frequency	%
Position held within the farm		
Farm employee / worker	34	12%

Owner / farm manager	229	83%
Other	14	5%
Gender		
Female	56	20%
Male	215	78%
Diverse	4	1%
Marital status		
Divorced	8	3%
Married / partnership	177	64%
Single	75	27%
Widowed	1	0%
Other	14	5%
Level of education		
Primary education	1	0%
Secondary education	60	22%
Tertiary education – Short course	55	20%
Tertiary education –Bachelor’s	60	22%
Tertiary education –Master’s	87	32%
Tertiary education –Doctoral	12	4%
Income (€)		
<=15000	78	28%
>15000 <=45000	122	44%

>45000 <= 105000	36	13%
>105000	42	15%
Years farming		
<=10	110	45%
11-20	61	25%
21-30	54	22%
>30	20	8%

Tab 2 – Sociodemographic characteristics.

	Frequency	%
Farm total area (ha)		
<=10	31	11%
>10 <=50	71	26%
>50 <= 100	53	19%
>100	123	44%
Farm's legal status		
Family farm / single enterprise	232	84%
Group holding	32	12%
Other	13	5%
Main production system		
Mixed cropping	18	7%
Mixed crops-livestock	102	37%
Specialist field (arable) crops	100	36%

Specialist horticulture	17	6%
Specialist permanent crops	23	8%
Other	17	6%
Geographical indication e.g. PDO or PGI.	32	12%
Organic farm	74	27%
Main crop grown on the farm		
Barley	24	9%
Maize	17	6%
Olives	14	5%
Potatoes	9	3%
Rapeseed	4	1%
Vegetables (indoor)	6	2%
Vegetables (outdoor)	15	5%
Wheat	85	31%
Other	103	37%

Tab 3 – Farm structural characteristics.

As we can see from Table 2, the majority of the sample is the owner or manager of the farm (83%), with an overrepresentation of males (78%) versus females. Married is the marital status more frequent.

The level of education varies substantially, underlying the different educational backgrounds among farmers. The distribution of years of farming shows a balanced representation across different experience levels, from less than ten years to over thirty years. Passing to the farm's structural characteristics, it is notable that 42% of the sample exceeds 100 hectares, indicating a prevalence of big farms with respect to the European average. Most of the farms are family-owned or single enterprises (84%). The specialization most represented is the mixed crop and livestock (37%), followed by specialists in arable crops (36%). A reasonably high

percentage of the interviewees are organic farmers (27%), and about one-tenth of the sample (12%) makes use of geographical indication certifications (e.g., PGI and PDO).

3.4.2. The farmers' opinion

Here, the results of the analysis of the answers to the questionnaire are presented. Farmers had to respond about two main points relative to the ECOSTACK measures. The first regards the adoption of the practices by the farmers. The second point focused on the farmers' opinions about the compatibility of the ECOSTACK strategies with their farm management. Hence, farmers were asked if they had carried out each of the measures on the farm in the past and indicated the top three most appropriate measures for their farm. The results are displayed in Fig 5 and Fig 6.

Fig 5 – Share of ECOSTACK measures carried out by the interviewed farmers.

Fig 6 – Top three compatible measures with the agricultural management of the farmer.

The most adopted measure is "Grass margin field" followed by "Under-sowing" and "Variety or cultivar mixture". On the opposite, "Trap cropping" and "Biopesticides" are the least adopted. With respect to the compatibility of the measures with farm management, almost a third of the sample (24%) indicate "no-tillage or direct seeding" as the most appropriate, highlighting the importance farmers give to soil management. Following, there are "Under-sowing" and "Green margin fields", in line with the measures adopted. The least compatible are "Trap cropping" and "Biopesticides", confirming the previous answer.

3.5. Highlight on Food Security and Environmental Sustainability

3.5.1. Introduction

Fast-evolving scenarios are arguably the critical characteristic the EU food system is constantly facing. Local and global scale phenomena, environmental and social aspects, the EU food policy has to deal with a variety of different challenges, each demanding a tailored solution. Climate change, on the one hand, emerges as a

pivotal factor, requiring dedicated policy interventions to soften the agricultural system's burden on the environment (Crippa et al., 2021). On the other hand, the European food system is being challenged as never before in recent history by the health crisis (in particular, the COVID-19 pandemic) (Laborde et al., 2021), the consequences of climate change (Abbass et al., 2022), and the conflict between Russian and Ukraine (Ben Hassen & El Bilali, 2022; Xu et al., 2023). The continued pressure exerted by these external factors poses the question of whether sustainability and food security can be pursued without a trade-off between the two. New food policies should be informed of the risks of incompatibility associated with food security and sustainability. European agricultural policy has always been at the forefront when it comes to innovating the agricultural system in the direction of environmental sustainability (Rayner et al., 2008). The present Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) makes no exception. The introduction of green architecture, merging Pillar I and Pillar II into the eco-strategies, goes in the same direction. Even though the effectiveness of these measures is still to be demonstrated, the EU's commitment to environmental sustainability is unquestionable. In this path of transition towards a more sustainable European food system, the fast-changing scenario raises the uncertainty related to different moments of the food supply chain, causing the necessity to review the CAP's basic ideas. Since its birth in 1957 with the Treaty establishing the European Economic Community, the European food system has ensured an increasing quantity and quality of food to citizens (Bureau & Swinnen, 2018). This has been achieved with the combination of technological innovation, generalised economic growth, and the application of effective policies (Bureau & Swinnen, 2018). EU past policies, in particular market direct interventions and coupled payments, increased agricultural productivity to a satisfying level already at the end of the past century. Thereafter, EU policy gradually abandoned these measures because they were no longer necessary (Becker, 2009); in other words, food security has no longer been of any concern since the beginning of the 21st century. Paradoxically, food surpluses were more problematic than deficits¹. Since then, a lot has changed, and new problems and perspectives shape agrifood policy priorities. The new fast-evolving context is characterised by continued shocks of different natures, and today's food system policy is partially directed to enhance the food system's resilience to crisis. The major shocks that pressure the system are climate change, COVID-19 and its economic consequences (even though its effects are almost entirely over) and Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Concerns also come by the rising risk of new similar shocks. Climate change's detrimental impact on agricultural production is known, and literature confirming and measuring this effect is consistent (Olesen & Bindi, 2002; Schröter et al., 2005). The COVID-19 epidemic has provoked a severe economic crisis, reducing everyone's access to a balanced and healthy diet. Russia's invasion of Ukraine has had manifold effects on the European (and global) food system (Belik, 2020; Nemes et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2023). First, it has generated an economic crisis due to the rise in the cost of energy. This reflects in higher costs of nitrogen fertilisers and, thus, higher general production costs for agricultural products. Second, both Russia and Ukraine are important exporters of different food commodities, in particular wheat and sunflower oil. The war influences the possibility of trading these commodities smoothly. However, the impact of these shocks on the European food system showed the incredible strength of the latter. During the first COVID-19 outbreak, there was not any shortage of food commodities, if not temporary. The war between Russia and Ukraine did not result in any concrete food security problem. "Food supply is not

¹ It is important to note that this is not the case in many other contexts, where food crises exist, rise in number and provoke severe consequences. We recommend reading the Global Report on Food Crises (GRFC, 2023) to investigate this aspect further.

at stake in the EU today". This is what the European Commission states in a communication published in March 2022 (European Commission, 2022). In this document, the Commission highlights the swift European responses to COVID-19 and the war. On the other hand, it also notes that food affordability for the low-income population is currently threatened. Hence, food security is still fully accomplished for the European population, but new environmental, geopolitical, and health issues raise the necessity of bringing the concept back to light. In fact, vulnerabilities in the European food system emerged (Belik, 2020; Moragues-Faus et al., 2017)). In order to enhance the resilience of the European food system, a group of experts called the European Food Security Crisis preparedness and response Mechanism (EFSCM) has been created. Moreover, the first concrete actions in this direction are already in place, as noted in the previously cited communication of the European Commission (European Commission 2022). Among these, the derogation from certain Greening obligations. The Greening is a list of indications farmers must follow in order to receive the subsidies. Notably, all these measures are not aimed at solving the problem of food security but at preparing the food system in order to avoid any future one. In this context of raised attention to food security across Europe (Borychowski et al., 2022), the question of the compatibility of these security measures and the EU sustainability objectives should be fully addressed, and priorities should be stated. Whether environmental sustainability and food security can be pursued synergetically or are mutually exclusive is an open debate. Recently, some authors have tried to investigate the affinity between the two goals, explicitly concerning the food system, yielding different results. Borychowski *et al.* (2022) highlight the lack of synergy between the environmental component and the food nutrition and security dimension. On the other hand, Vågsholm et al. (2020) advise that food security and environmental sustainability are both pillars of a sustainable future and should be sought together. In this context of uncertainty related to the interaction of the two aspects, policymakers should be fully informed and assisted by the relevant literature to find the best policy options. To conclude, sustainability might increase food security by making the food system more resilient in the medium-long term, but in the short term, it seems like there could be a conflict between the two concepts. Literature should address the problem to provide policymakers with information to produce better and fully informed policies. In order to shed light on the relationship between environmental sustainability and food security from a policy perspective and to provide valuable material to policymakers, a two-step Delphi procedure has been carried out. The Delphi method is a well-known structured communication technique aimed at gathering and clarifying knowledge from a group of experts to make informed decisions or predictions (Delbecq et al., 1986). The RAND Corporation first developed the Delphi method to forecast the impact of technological advances in high-uncertainty cold war scenarios (Dalkey, 1969; Ziglio & Adler, 1996). Through the years, numerous research domains have made use of the Delphi technique (Doyon & Labrecque, 2008; Humphrey-Murto et al., 2017; Lin & Song, 2015), thus becoming a prominent methodology in the qualitative research area (Brady, 2015). The Delphi provides a structured and iterative approach to understanding a subject matter by using the collective wisdom of a diverse group of participants (Jorm, 2015). The method is particularly useful when there is uncertainty, complexity, and a need for consensus among experts (Donohoe & Needham, 2009; Gray & Hovav, 2008). The Delphi method typically involves multiple rounds of data collection and analysis. In the first round, a panel of experts is selected based on their knowledge and expertise in the relevant field. These experts are then presented with a series of questionnaires or structured interviews that aim to elicit their judgments, opinions, and insights on the subject being studied. Once the responses are collected, they are anonymised and summarised by the researchers. In subsequent rounds, the experts are provided with feedback from the previous round, including

summaries of the group's responses and any areas of disagreement or consensus. This feedback serves as a basis for re-evaluating their initial judgments and reiterating their opinions. The Delphi method encourages experts to reconsider their positions in light of the collective feedback, leading to a convergence of opinions over multiple rounds. The goal of the Delphi method is to reach a level of consensus or convergence among the participating experts. The method's strength lies in its ability to generate valuable information and recommendations, inform decision-making processes, and provide a deeper understanding of complex issues through the collective wisdom of experts.

3.5.2. Materials and methods

A two-stage Delphi study was developed to explore the relationships between environmental sustainability and food security in the European agrifood sector. The data gathering was carried out between May 2023 and October 2023. The first round was focused on highlighting the general strengths and vulnerabilities of the European agrifood sector and gathering the expert's opinions on the relationship between environmental sustainability and food security, especially regarding synergies and trade-offs between the two aspects. The second round was built on the responses of the first round and asked the experts to review the emerging consensus and disagreement among the respondents.

The panel

The recruitment was carried out within the Horizon 2020 project ECOSTACK. Several renowned universities and research institutes primarily dedicated to research in the agrifood sector participated in the project. The academic members of the project were asked to propose experts in agrifood policy or people involved in agrifood policy development in the European context at different scales. Both local and communitarian policymakers were contacted. The search for participants ended when the ideal number for a Delphi study was achieved. The final number of experts who accepted to participate was fifteen. The experts represented four different European countries. Those are Germany, Italy, Spain and Sweden.

Round one

The first round introduced the study to the experts, giving the basic ideas and concepts of the Delphi procedure. Anonymity was assured to the experts, and the process of iteration and feedback was described. At this stage, questions are broader, and the experts are given the possibility to express their opinions with open-ended questions. This part consisted of a questionnaire divided into two sections. In the first section, there were two open-ended questions asking about the strengths and weaknesses of the current agricultural policy. Moreover, experts were asked to rate from 1 (Not important) to 7 (very important) the ten CAP objectives. Finally, participants could indicate objectives that should be added to the list in the future, if any. The second part of the first round introduced the topic of the study to the experts, with a short text explaining the research questions. Hereafter, experts gave their opinion on the adequateness of the CAP's Green Architecture to the sustainability goals, on the difficulties farmers may encounter in following the regulations related to the eco-schemes and on the adequateness of the technical and scientific support given to the farmers to accomplish the norms. Then, experts were asked to express themselves about the level of

accomplishment of food security for European citizens in the present times and in the near future. In conclusion, experts gave their opinion on the possible trade-offs between environmental sustainability and food security and stated the relative importance of the two concepts.

Round two

The second round consisted of a questionnaire divided into two parts. With respect to the first round, questions were more closed-ended, and experts could indicate the level of consensus with the results of the first round. The first part gathered the level of agreement about thirteen salient points that emerged from the first round with a sufficient level of consensus. The second part was dedicated to opinions that did not find an acceptable level of consensus. In this part, three questions from the previous round were asked again. In addition to the questions, experts read a brief argument covering both the possible opposing opinions and saw the anonymous answers from the previous round of the entire panel.

3.5.3. Results

Round one

The first round was composed of a mixture of open-ended and close-ended questions that were managed differently. The open-ended questions were analysed by looking at the frequency of the emergence of certain concepts. Those that at least four experts exposed were considered for the sequent round. The shared ideas are reported in Table 4.

One of the CAP's greatest strengths is related to its overall strategy.
One of the greatest strengths of the CAP is related to environmental sustainability goals and achievements in this area.
One of the greatest strengths of the CAP is related to the economic support provided to farmers, which enables the protection of the entire European agricultural sector.
One of the biggest weaknesses of the CAP is that it fails to capture the specificities of the different realities in the EU.
One of the biggest weaknesses of the CAP is having a complicated management and not having highly effective tools for evaluating the results of it's actions.
The most important objectives of the CAP are: efficient natural resource management; Halting and

reversing biodiversity loss; Contribute to climate change mitigation.
The current Green Architecture is only partly adapted to Europe's sustainability goals.
A limitation of the current policy with regard to sustainability is that it has to mediate between the interests of different actors in the supply chain.
The current implementation of Eco-schemes by farmers is only partly feasible. There are several reasons for this: a high number of tools and a design that is poorly correlated with production and territorial realities.
Technical and scientific support to farmers is inadequate. In particular, public support structures are lacking and private support is insufficient.

Tab 4 – Concepts emerged from the first section of the first round.

The evaluation of the importance of the CAP objectives was positive, with every objective scoring more than five out of seven on average. The specific results for each objective are shown in Figure 7. Detailed summary statistics are shown in Table 5.

CAP objectives importance

Fig 7 – CAP objectives perceived importance.

CAP objective	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max
Supporting viable farm income	5.73	2.11	1	7

Increasing competitiveness	5.47	2.28	1	7
Improving farmers' position in the value chain	5.87	2.08	1	7
Contributing to climate change mitigation	6.2	1.08	4	7
Efficient natural resource management	6.4	1.39	4	7
Halting and reversing biodiversity loss	6.33	1.30	5	7
Generational renewal	5.6	2.24	1	7
Jobs, growth and equality in rural areas	5.53	2.04	2	7
Responding to societal demands on food & health	5.47	2.28	1	7
Fostering knowledge & innovation	6.13	1.39	4	7

Tab 5 – CAP objectives perceived importance summary statistics.

The objectives valued more by the panel are the ones related to the environmental aspects of the CAP. On the other hand, the ones that scored the least are "Increasing competitiveness" and "Responding to societal demands on food and health". Regarding the second section of the first round, consensus was scarce. Figure 8 shows the responses to the second section of the first round.

Fig 8 – Result of the second section of the first round.

Nonetheless, there are three points shared by the experts for this section, and they are listed in Table 6. While the food security at the present situation is not at risk for the panel, in future perspective experts have diverse opinions.

Food security is not at risk in the present situation for EU citizens.
The goals of sustainability and food security are equally important and should be pursued with the same priority.
Although only partially, there may be a trade-off between ensuring food security and pursuing environmental sustainability.

Tab 6 – Concepts emerged from the second section of the first round.

Round two

In the second round, the panel consisted of thirteen experts due to the drop-out of two respondents. In this round, experts indicated their level of accordance with the emerging concepts of the first round. The concepts

and the summary statistics of the resulting accordance on a scale from 1 (=strongly disagree) to 7 (=strongly agree) are reported in Table 7. The accordance was high for all the concepts. Notably, "One of the biggest weaknesses of the CAP is having a complicated management and not having highly effective tools for evaluating the results of its actions" and "The goals of sustainability and food security are equally important and should be pursued with the same priority" scored the highest average value. On the other hand, the topics that scored the lowest were "One of the biggest weaknesses of the CAP is that it fails to capture the specificities of the different realities in the EU" and "The current implementation of Eco-schemes by farmers is only partly feasible. There are several reasons for this: a high number of tools and a design that is poorly correlated with production and territorial realities".

CAP objective	Mean	St. Dev.	Min	Max
One of the CAP's greatest strengths is related to its overall strategy.	5.31	1.11	3	7
One of the greatest strengths of the CAP is related to environmental sustainability goals and achievements in this area.	5.31	0.85	4	7
One of the greatest strengths of the CAP is related to the economic support provided to farmers, which enables the protection of the entire European agricultural sector.	5.00	1.53	1	7
One of the biggest weaknesses of the CAP is that it fails to capture the specificities of the different realities in the EU.	4.08	1.66	1	7
One of the biggest weaknesses of the CAP is having complicated management and not having highly effective tools for evaluating the results of its actions.	5.69	0.95	4	7
The most important objectives of the CAP are: efficient natural resource management; Halting and reversing biodiversity loss; Contributing to climate change mitigation.	5.31	1.18	4	7
The current Green Architecture is only partly adapted to Europe's sustainability goals.	4.69	1.44	1	7

A limitation of the current policy with regard to sustainability is that it has to mediate between the interests of different actors in the supply chain.	4.62	1.50	2	6
The current implementation of Eco-schemes by farmers is only partly feasible. There are several reasons for this: a high number of tools and a design that is poorly correlated with production and territorial realities.	4.54	1.71	2	7
Technical and scientific support to farmers is inadequate. In particular, public support structures are lacking and private support is insufficient.	5.38	1.76	2	7
Food security is not at risk in the present situation for EU citizens.	5.38	1.56	2	7
The goals of sustainability and food security are equally important and should be pursued with the same priority.	5.62	1.12	3	7
Although only partially, there may be a trade-off between ensuring food security and pursuing environmental sustainability.	5.08	1.26	2	7

Tab 7 – Evaluation of the emerging concepts.

The answers of the second section of the second round are shown in Figure 9. Those answers were related to the topics with low consensus in the previous round.

Fig 8 – Result of the low consensus questions.

Notably, results in this section show a higher level of consensus for all the questions. In particular, the panel strongly agree that in the upcoming years, food security will be threatened more than today. Moreover, the experts agree that there will be a trade-off between guaranteeing food security and pursuing environmental sustainability in the future and that the current policy is adequate to guarantee food security in the actual socio-economical and environmental scenario.

3.6. Guidelines for future policies

Agricultural support policies are strategic for achieving environmentally sustainable food production.

The new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) 2023-2027 has been in place since January 2023. This new policy has the ambition to raise the environmental performance of European agriculture. The Green Architecture of the policy is composed of three different but integrated tools: conditionality, eco-schemes, and agri-environment and climate measures (Peeters et al., 2021).

Implementing policy guidelines that are more suited to the ecological strategies implemented by the project requires two different temporal steps. The first one is the current CAP 2023-2027, where the structure of the interventions is already fixed. The second one may provide some indications regarding the next programming period.

The ecostack strategies implemented by the project aren't simple innovations in production processes but a real change in the vision of agricultural production. In the current structure of interventions, eco-schemes and agri-environmental measures could represent, if well calibrated, a room to support such changes. However,

where possible, it is necessary, in the programmed maintenance of interventions, to identify specific activities and estimate adequate support payments for farms. Indeed, the actions envisaged by public intervention must be technically feasible and economically viable.

A greater possibility of adapting interventions for increased support in adopting ecostack strategies can be offered by the green architecture, and all interventions can be dedicated to knowledge transfer and innovation. The cross-cutting objective of CAP 2023-2027 aims to 'foster and share knowledge, innovation, and digitalization in agriculture and rural areas, and encourage their uptake by farmers, through improved access to research, innovation, knowledge exchange, and training' (Article 5).

The strategies to achieve the cross-cutting objective include intensive knowledge exchange and competent advisors within the Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS), co-creating and sharing innovation, and adopting digitalization tools. In particular, AKIS encompass all individuals and organizations (farmers, foresters, farmers' and foresters' organizations and cooperatives, advisors, researchers, businesses, NGOs, etc.) that generate, share, and use knowledge and innovation for agriculture and related fields such as rural areas, value chains, environment, climate, biodiversity, society, consumers, etc. These strategies could serve as drivers for the ecological transition of the agricultural sector (Krishna et al., 2023; Langlais, 2023).

In addition to the specific actions mentioned, which include training, advice, information, and demonstration, there are other tools characterised by high strategic value in the chapter dedicated to Rural Development of the current CAP. The current CAP (2023-2027) provides opportunities for preparing and implementing Operational Group (OG) projects and LEADER initiatives with Local Action Groups (LAG) implementation. An OG project is a group of people with complementary knowledge (e.g., practical, scientific, technical, organisational expertise, etc.) who co-create practical solutions for agriculture, forestry, and rural communities in an innovation project. On the other hand, the well-known European program LEADER aims to involve local actors in rural areas in developing their regions by forming LAGs and designing and implementing strategies. Until now, more than 2500 LAGs have been established, covering over 50% of the rural population in the EU.

Finally, we could also include in this segment other cooperation measures implemented in the current CAP, such as 'cooperation for local development' and 'extension services for farms'. The most important pillar for all interventions is innovation.

Public institutions responsible for agriculture in different countries could leverage this group of European interventions to promote a greater diffusion of knowledge about the ecological strategies implemented and to support their adoption. In particular, by applying a systemic approach to consulting, training, OGs, and LAGs activities, it would also be possible to customize the innovations produced by the project further according to the productive and environmental characteristics of the involved areas.

For the European Agricultural Policy post-2027, drawing possible guidelines becomes more challenging.

The climate and biodiversity crises and economic and political crises must be considered in shaping a new European agricultural and food model (Lankoski & Lankoski, 2023). Ecological innovations have to be supported by public intervention, not considering them as separate actions but as a new approach to the production process. Following this path, public interventions for knowledge transfer, advisory services,

training for farmers and advisors, and tutoring services during the transition phase, especially for young farmers, will remain key elements for disseminating and adopting ecological practices.

A more efficient science-policy interface will also be needed. What today's challenges and the planning of public intervention ask policymakers are not feasible without collaboration between science and policy. There is still much to be done on this. European Green Architecture tools could be much more impactful if they had stronger technical content and if the structuring of the agri-environmental intervention had resulted from a well-structured science-policy interface.

4. Conclusions

The analysis involved farmers and policymakers. With farmers, we investigated the compatibility of EcoStack strategies with production processes and their adoption by farms. The study investigated with policymakers which instruments of the CAP were best suited to support the strategies implemented by the project. It also examined how changes in the socio-economic and policy scenarios will influence European intervention in agriculture, balancing opposing objectives of productivity and sustainability.

The aim of EcoStack is to promote sustainable crop production by enhancing ecosystem services provision and protecting functional biodiversity. This aligns with the greening process of the Cap, which has transformed the vision and production processes of European agriculture over the past 30 years. Between 2011 and 2021, the total volume of pesticides sold in the 16 European countries decreased by 4.9%. This decrease provides evidence of the reduction in pesticide use.

It is a challenging task, however, to reconcile the need for increased agricultural productivity to meet the growing demand for food with environmental sustainability. The COVID-19 pandemic and ongoing conflicts have further highlighted the conflicting objectives of productivity and environmental protection in the long-term development vision of European agriculture.

The new CAP 2023-2027 has implemented numerous instruments to protect the environment, resources, and biodiversity. All measures, including the new green architecture of the European agricultural policy, have been integrated into Pillar I and II with the introduction of the eco-schemes. According to policymakers interviewed, eco-schemes are useful tools to support and disseminate innovative environmental behaviours, including many EcoStack strategies. The farmers interviewed reported that the EcoStack strategies most commonly adopted are those that find support in European policy interventions, such as grass margin fields, variety or cultivar mixtures, and no-tillage or direct seeding. On the other hand, trap cropping and biopesticides are considered the least compatible. It is important to note that the low adoption of biopesticides and microorganisms requires further investigation. Biopesticides are a viable alternative to conventional pesticides. However, their low adoption of these is a limit that should be investigated more. In order to achieve the same increase in usage as expected in North America by 2029 (+29.5% - Global Biopesticides Market, 2023), strategies must be developed to find an

acceptable trade-off between productivity and sustainability in Europe. However, this possible path requires different but integrated strategies. Research, advisory services and knowledge dissemination are the real strategic elements.

EcoStack strategies and a comprehensive agroecological approach require not only the adoption of alternative production techniques or products for crop protection but also a different vision of production process management. This can be achieved through economic incentives for specific actions, as well as the implementation of advisory and innovation support services for production changes and innovation adoption in the medium and long run.

The second step of the study, the Delphi analysis, revealed a conflict between the two previously mentioned objectives: sustainability and productivity/food security. The results indicate that the most important objectives of the CAP for respondents are "Contributing to climate change mitigation", "Efficient natural resource management", and "Halting and reversing biodiversity loss". However, the objectives of "Increasing competitiveness", "Responding to Societal demands on food & health", and "Generational renewal, Jobs, growth and equality in rural areas" are considered less important. This is a significant limitation of current public intervention, particularly in recent protest scenarios affecting the European agricultural sector.

The agricultural sector faces various challenges, including climate change and new demographic and market scenarios. Therefore, public policy must support the economic dimension of farms.

The Delphi results indicate that the interviewed experts have reached a high consensus on critical issues. For instance, policymakers have declared a high level of agreement regarding the questions 'Will food security be more threatened in the upcoming years than it is today?' and "Will there be a trade-off between guaranteeing food security and pursuing environmental sustainability in the future?".

The consensus suggests that the issues to be addressed are now clear in the policymakers' vision. However, experts have concluded that the current European policy is not sufficiently adapted to achieve the desired results. The current situation in the agricultural sector indicates that this is indeed the case. The prioritization of rethinking sustainability from a new perspective, accelerating research in areas that make agroecology more applicable in its holistic dimension, and implementing a more efficient science-policy interface are still necessary.

References

Abbass, K., Qasim, M. Z., Song, H., Murshed, M., Mahmood, H., & Younis, I. (2022). A review of the global climate change impacts, adaptation, and sustainable mitigation measures. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(28), 42539–42559. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-022-19718-6>

- Becker, T. (2009). European Food Quality Policy: The Importance of Geographical Indications, Organic Certification and Food Quality Assurance Schemes in European Countries. *Estey Centre Journal of International Law and Trade Policy*, 10.
- Belik, W. (2020). Sustainability and food security after COVID-19: relocalizing food systems? *Agricultural and Food Economics*, 8(1), 23. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40100-020-00167-z>
- Ben Hassen, T., & El Bilali, H. (2022). Impacts of the Russia-Ukraine War on Global Food Security: Towards More Sustainable and Resilient Food Systems? *Foods*, 11(15), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods11152301>
- Borychowski, M., Sapa, A., Czyżewski, B., Stępień, S., & Poczta-Wajda, A. (2022). Interactions between food and nutrition security and the socio-economic and environmental dimensions of sustainability in small-scale farms: evidence from a simultaneous confirmatory factor analysis in Poland. *International Journal of Agricultural Sustainability*, 20(5), 998–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14735903.2022.2041230>
- Brady, S. R. (2015). Utilizing and Adapting the Delphi Method for Use in Qualitative Research. *International Journal of Qualitative Methods*, 14(5). <https://doi.org/10.1177/1609406915621381>
- Bureau, J.-C., & Swinnen, J. (2018). EU policies and global food security. *Global Food Security*, 16, 106–115. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfs.2017.12.001>
- Crippa, M., Solazzo, E., Guizzardi, D., Monforti-Ferrario, F., Tubiello, F. N., & Leip, A. (2021). Food systems are responsible for a third of global anthropogenic GHG emissions. *Nature Food*, 2(3), 198–209. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43016-021-00225-9>
- Dalkey, N. (1969). An experimental study of group opinion: The Delphi method. *Futures*, 1(5). [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287\(69\)80025-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-3287(69)80025-X)
- Delbecq, A., Ven, A., & Gustafson, D. (1986). Group Techniques for Program Planning: A Guide to Nominal Group and Delphi Processes. *Glenview, Illinois: Scott Forman and Co.*
- Donohoe, H. M., & Needham, R. D. (2009). Moving best practice forward: Delphi characteristics, advantages, potential problems, and solutions. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 11(5), 415–437. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.709>
- Doyon, M., & Labrecque, J. (2008). Functional Foods: A Conceptual Definition. *British Food Journal*, 110, 1133–1149. <https://doi.org/10.1108/00070700810918036>
- European Commission. (2022). *Safeguarding food security and reinforcing the resilience of food systems*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/doi/10.2777/51295>
- Gray, P., & Hovav, A. (2008). From Hindsight to Foresight: Applying Futures Research Techniques in Information Systems. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.17705/1CAIS.02212>

- Humphrey-Murto, S., Varpio, L., Wood, T. J., Gonsalves, C., Ufholz, L.-A., Mascioli, K., Wang, C., & Foth, T. (2017). The Use of the Delphi and Other Consensus Group Methods in Medical Education Research: A Review. *Academic Medicine*, 92(10), 1491–1498. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000001812>
- Jorm, A. F. (2015). Using the Delphi expert consensus method in mental health research. *Australian & New Zealand Journal of Psychiatry*, 49(10), 887–897. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0004867415600891>
- Laborde, D., Martin, W., & Vos, R. (2021). Impacts of COVID-19 on global poverty, food security, and diets: Insights from global model scenario analysis. *Agricultural Economics (United Kingdom)*, 52(3), 375–390. <https://doi.org/10.1111/agec.12624>
- Lankoski, J., & Lankoski, L. (2023). Environmental sustainability in agriculture: Identification of bottlenecks. *Ecological Economics*, 204, 107656. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2022.107656>
- Lin, V. S., & Song, H. (2015). A review of Delphi forecasting research in tourism. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 18(12), 1099–1131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2014.967187>
- Moragues-Faus, A., Sonnino, R., & Marsden, T. (2017). Exploring European food system vulnerabilities: Towards integrated food security governance. *Environmental Science and Policy*, 75(May), 184–215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2017.05.015>
- Nemes, G., Chiffolleau, Y., Zollet, S., Collison, M., Benedek, Z., Colantuono, F., Dulsrud, A., Fiore, M., Holtkamp, C., Kim, T.-Y., Korzun, M., Mesa-Manzano, R., Reckinger, R., Ruiz-Martínez, I., Smith, K., Tamura, N., Viteri, M. L., & Orbán, É. (2021). The impact of COVID-19 on alternative and local food systems and the potential for the sustainability transition: Insights from 13 countries. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 28, 591–599. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.06.022>
- Olesen, & Bindi. (2002). Consequences of climate change for European agricultural productivity. *Land Use and Policy*, 16, 239–262. www.elsevier.com/locate/eja
- Peeters, A., Lefebvre, O., Balogh, L., Bàrberi, P., Batello, C., Bellon, S., Gaifami, T., Gkisakis, V., Lana, M., Migliorini, P., Ostermann, O., & Wezel, A. (2021). *A Green Deal for implementing agroecological systems: Reforming the Common Agricultural Policy of the European Union*. 70, 83–93. <https://doi.org/10.3220/LBF1610123299000>
- Rayner, G., Barling, D., & Lang, T. (2008). Sustainable food systems in europe: Policies, realities and futures. *Journal of Hunger and Environmental Nutrition*, 3(2–3), 145–168. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19320240802243209>
- Schröter, D., Cramer, W., Leemans, R., Prentice, I. C., Araújo, M. B., Arnell, N. W., Bondeau, A., Bugmann, H., Carter, T. R., Gracia, C. A., De La Vega-Leinert, A. C., Erhard, M., Ewert, F., Glendining, M., House, J. I., Kankaanpää, S., Klein, R. J. T., Lavorel, S., Lindner, M., ... Zierl, B. (2005). Ecology: Ecosystem service supply and vulnerability to global change in Europe. *Science*, 310(5752), 1333–1337. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1115233>

Vågsholm, I., Arzoomand, N. S., & Boqvist, S. (2020). Food Security, Safety, and Sustainability—Getting the Trade-Offs Right. *Frontiers in Sustainable Food Systems*, 4(February), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.00016>

Xu, Y., Wang, Z., Dong, W., & Chou, J. (2023). Predicting the Potential Impact of Emergency on Global Grain Security: A Case of the Russia–Ukraine Conflict. *Foods*, 12(13), 2557. <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods12132557>

Ziglio, E., & Adler, M. (1996). *Gazing into the oracle : the Delphi method and its application to social policy and public health*. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:141511920>

Directive 2009/128/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 21 October 2009 establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides

Charan Krishna, Jesse Donham, Alexander Wezel. Eco-schemes in EU member states could benefit from more agroecology (Policy brief). *Agroecology for Europe (AE4EU)*. 2023.

Langlais A. The new Common Agricultural Policy: reflecting an agro-ecological transition. The legal perspective. *Rev Agric Food Environ Stud*. 2023;104(1):51-66.